

ULAANBAATAR STATE UNIVERSITY
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS AND ELECTRONICS

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RADON MONITORING AND MEASUREMENT
OF EMEELT ACTIVE FAULT

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Ulaanbaatar city

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ULAANBAATAR STATE UNIVERSITY
DEPARTMENT OF PHYSICS AND ELECTRONICS

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RADON MONITORING AND MEASUREMENT
OF EMEELT ACTIVE FAULT

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MOTIVATION

MOTIVATION

The radon gas is produced by the radioactive decay of the uranium traces present in the most rocks. The radon measurements have played important roles in many fields, such as but not limited to health physics, mining and milling industries, public water supplies, real estate transactions, and geophysical studies. The problems of radon diffusion, detection and measurement have been studied widely since the middle of the last century. It was suggested that by continues time measurements for radon gas can be predicted earthquake on a specific time. Therefore, such the short time measurement of radon gas for fault zone detection is very important task in geophysical research.

THESIS OBJECTIVES

Objective of this research is study of fault systems around the Ulaanbaatar such as Emeelt, Khustai, Avdar and Gunj. Research has been conducted for 8 years. Among them Emeelt fault such as “Ehen-US” shows a high seismic activity zone.

ORIGINALITY

The first time, two different types of detectors were used for thorough research of 1 fault’s radon activity and are being connected to the seismic activity. Also, this study is the first in Mongolia by its consistent monitoring with permanent stations and real-time analysis in geophysical research.

Usually, previous research for radon studies were performed on determination of radioactivity level of of drinking water and groundwater.

INTRODUCTION

INTRODUCTION

The most natural rocks contain small amounts of gases which can be different isotopes from the normal atmospheric gases. The scientists have observed spikes in the concentrations of such gases prior to a major earthquake; this has been attributed to the release of pre-seismic stress and fracturing of the rock. One of these gases is radon, produced by the radioactive decay of the uranium traces present in most rocks. International seismic researchers showed that the monitoring of radon activity could predict earthquakes from the specific time before it occurs.

Soil monitoring of radon is believed to be able to detect earthquakes specific time before they occur, according to many scientists around the world. The Institute of Astronomy and Geophysics installed 8 radon probes on the Khustain and Emeelt seismic faults which are very close to the city (respectively 130 km and 20 km far from the city). The institute focuses its research on 2 probes placed right on the seismic activity fault of Khustain, 5 probes on the seismic activity fault of Emeelt and another probe which is not on a fault. The probes on the Khustain fault didn't show any anomaly of radon activity since their installation (in 2012), but the Emeelt probes (installed in July 2009) measured many anomalies of radon activity. Khustain fault has only a few earthquakes and Emeelt fault is very active: around 500 earthquakes each year. All these earthquakes have low magnitudes. During the last two years, every time that the probes on Emeelt fault measured anomalies in radon activity, several shocks happened around 20 days later. Those results are currently discussed amongst the scientific community to determine whether the radon can be considered as a precursor of seismic activity and under debate.

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

1.1 The internal structure of the earth

The internal structure of the Earth is layered in spherical shells: an outer silicate solid crust, a highly viscous asthenosphere and mantle, a liquid outer core that is much less viscous than the mantle, and a solid inner core. Scientific understanding of the internal structure of the earth is based on observations of topography and bathymetry, observations of rock in outcrop, samples brought to the surface from greater depths by volcanoes or volcanic activity, analysis of the seismic waves that pass through the Earth, measurements of the gravitational and magnetic fields of the Earth, and experiments with crystalline solids at pressures and temperatures characteristic of the Earth's deep interior (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The internal structure of the earth.

1.1.1 Structure

The structure of Earth can be defined in two ways: by mechanical properties such as rheology, or chemically. Mechanically, it can be divided into lithosphere, asthenosphere, mesospheric mantle, outer core, and the inner core. Chemically, Earth can be divided into the crust, upper mantle, lower mantle, outer core, and inner core. The geologic component layers of Earth [1] are at the following depths below the surface:

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

Depth	Layer
Kilometres	
0–60	Lithosphere (locally varies between 5 and 200 km)
0–35	... Crust (locally varies between 5 and 70 km)
35–60	... Uppermost part of mantle
35–2,890	Mantle
210–270	... Upper mesosphere (upper mantle)
660–2,890	... Lower mesosphere (lower mantle)
2,890–5,150	Outer core
5,150–6,360	Inner core

Table 1. The internal layer of the earth depth

The layering of Earth has been inferred indirectly using the time of travel of refracted and reflected seismic waves created by earthquakes. The core does not allow shear waves to pass through it, while the speed of travel (seismic velocity) is different in other layers. The changes in seismic velocity between different layers causes refraction owing to Snell's law, like light bending as it passes through a prism. Likewise, reflections are caused by a large increase in seismic velocity and are similar to light reflecting from a mirror.

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

1.1.2 Crust

The crust ranges from 5–70 kilometers (3.1–43.5 mi) in depth and is the outermost layer (Figure 2). The thin parts are the oceanic crust, which underlie the ocean basins (5–10 km) and are composed of dense (mafic) iron magnesium silicate igneous rocks, like basalt. The thicker crust is continental crust, which is less dense and composed of (felsic) sodium potassium aluminum silicate rocks, like granite. The rocks of the crust fall into two major categories – sial and sima (Suess, 1831–1914). It is estimated that sima starts about 11 km below the Conrad discontinuity (a second order discontinuity). The uppermost mantle together with the crust constitutes the lithosphere. The crust-mantle boundary occurs as two physically different events. First, there is a discontinuity in the seismic velocity, which is most commonly known as the Mohorovicic discontinuity or Moho. The cause of the Moho is thought to be a change in rock composition from rocks containing plagioclase feldspar (above) to rocks that contain no feldspars (below). Second, in oceanic crust, there is a chemical discontinuity between ultramafic cumulates and tectonized harzburgites, which has been observed from deep parts of the oceanic crust that have been abducted onto the continental crust and preserved as ophiolite sequences.

Many rocks now making up Earth's crust formed less than 100 million (1×10^8) years ago; however, the oldest known mineral grains are about 4.4 billion (4.4×10^9) years old, indicating that Earth has had a solid crust for at least 4.4 billion years [2].

Figure 2. Earth structure

1.1.3 Mantle

Earth mantle extends to a depth of 2,890 km, making it the thickest layer of Earth. The mantle is divided into upper and lower mantle. The upper and lower mantle are separated by the transition zone. The lowest part of the mantle next to the core-mantle boundary is known as the D'' [3] layer. The pressure at the bottom of the mantle is ≈ 140 GPa (1.4 M atm). The mantle is composed of silicate rocks that are rich in iron and magnesium relative to the overlying crust. Although solid, the high temperatures within the mantle cause the silicate material to be sufficiently ductile that it can flow on very long timescales. Convection of the mantle is expressed at the surface through the motions of tectonic plates. As there is intense and increasing pressure as one travels deeper into the mantle, the lower part of the mantle flows less easily than does the upper mantle (chemical changes within the mantle may also be important). The viscosity of the mantle ranges between 10^{21} and 10^{24} Pa s, depending on depth [4]. In comparison, the viscosity of water is approximately 10^{-3} Pa s and that of pitch is 10^7 Pa·s. The source of heat that drives plate tectonics is the primordial heat left over from the planet's formation as well as the radioactive decay of uranium, thorium, and potassium in Earth's crust and mantle [5].

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

1.1.4 Core

The average density of Earth is 5.515 g/cm^3 [6]. Because the average density of surface material is only around 3.0 g/cm^3 , we must conclude that denser materials exist within Earth's core. This result has been known since the Schiehallion experiment, performed in the 1770s. Charles Hutton in his 1778 report concluded that the mean density of the Earth must be about $9/5$ that of surface rock, concluding that the interior of the Earth must be metallic. Hutton estimated this metallic portion to occupy some 65% of the diameter of the Earth [7] Hutton's estimate on the mean density of the Earth was still about 20% too low, at 4.5 g/cm^3 Henry Cavendish in his torsion balance experiment of 1798 found a value of 5.45 g/cm^3 , within 1% of the modern value [8]. Seismic measurements show that the core is divided into two parts, a "solid inner core with a radius of $\approx 1,220 \text{ km}$ [9] and a liquid outer core extending beyond it to a radius of $\approx 3,400 \text{ km}$. The densities are between $9,900$ and $12,200 \text{ kg/m}^3$ in the outer core and $12,600$ – $13,000 \text{ kg/m}^3$ in the inner core [10].

The inner core was discovered in 1936 by Inge Lehmann and is generally believed to be composed primarily of iron and some nickel. Since this layer is able to transmit shear waves (transverse seismic waves), it must be solid. Experimental evidence has at times been critical of crystal models of the core [11]. Other experimental studies show a discrepancy under high pressure: diamond anvil (static) studies at core pressures yield melting temperatures that are approximately 2000 K below those from shock laser (dynamic) studies [12]. The laser studies create plasma [13], and the results are suggestive that constraining inner core conditions will depend on whether the inner core is a solid or is a plasma with the density of a solid. This is an area of active research.

In early stages of Earth's formation about 4.6 billion years ago, melting would have caused denser substances to sink toward the center in a process called planetary differentiation, while less-dense materials would have migrated to the crust. The core is thus believed to largely be composed of iron (80%), along with nickel and one or more light elements, whereas other dense elements, such as lead and uranium, either are too rare to be significant or tend to bind to

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

lighter elements and thus remain in the crust (see felsic materials). Some have argued that the inner core may be in the form of a single iron crystal [14].

Under laboratory conditions a sample of iron–nickel alloy was subjected to the corelike pressures by gripping it in a vise between 2 diamond tips (diamond anvil cell), and then heating to approximately 4000 K. The sample was observed with x-rays, and strongly supported the theory that Earth's inner core was made of giant crystals running north to south [15]. The liquid outer core surrounds the inner core and is believed to be composed of iron mixed with nickel and trace amounts of lighter elements. Recent speculation suggests that the innermost part of the core is enriched in gold, platinum and other siderophile elements [16]. The matter that comprises Earth is connected in fundamental ways to matter of certain chondrite meteorites, and to matter of outer portion of the Sun [17]. There is good reason to believe that Earth is, in the main, like a chondrite meteorite. Beginning as early as 1940, scientists, including Francis Birch, built geophysics upon the premise that Earth is like ordinary chondrites, the most common type of meteorite observed impacting Earth, while totally ignoring another, albeit less abundant type called enstatite chondrites. The principal difference between the two meteorite types is that enstatite chondrites formed under circumstances of extremely limited available oxygen, leading to certain normally oxyphilic elements existing either partially or wholly in the alloy portion that corresponds to the core of Earth.

Dynamo theory suggests that convection in the outer core, combined with the Coriolis effect, gives rise to Earth's magnetic field. The solid inner core is too hot to hold a permanent magnetic field but probably acts to stabilize the magnetic field generated by the liquid outer core. The average magnetic field strength in Earth's outer core is estimated to be 25 Gauss (2.5 mT), 50 times stronger than the magnetic field at the surface [18].

Recent evidence has suggested that the inner core of Earth may rotate slightly faster than the rest of the planet [19] however more recent studies in 2011 found this hypothesis to be inconclusive. Options remain for the core which may be oscillatory in nature or a chaotic system. In August 2005 a team of

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

geophysicists announced in the journal *Science* that, according to their estimates, Earth's inner core rotates approximately 0.3 to 0.5 degrees per year faster relative to the rotation of the surface [20].

The current scientific explanation for Earth's temperature gradient is a combination of heat left over from the planet's initial formation, decay of radioactive elements, and freezing of the inner core.

1.2 Tectonic plates movement

Plate tectonics from the Late Latin (*tectonicus*), from the Greek: τεκτονικός "pertaining to building" (Fowler & Coulsen 1990) is a scientific theory describing the large-scale motion of seven large plates and the movements of a larger number of smaller plates of the Earth's lithosphere, since tectonic processes began on Earth between 3 and 3.5 billion years ago. The model builds on the concept of continental drift, an idea developed during the first decades of the 20th century. The geoscientific community accepted plate-tectonic theory after seafloor spreading was validated in the late 1950s and early 1960s.

The lithosphere, which is the rigid outermost shell of a planet (the crust and upper mantle), is broken into tectonic plates. The Earth's lithosphere is composed of seven or eight major plates (depending on how they are defined) and many minor plates. Where the plates meet, their relative motion determines the type of boundary: convergent, divergent, or transform.

Earthquakes volcanic activity, mountain-building, and oceanic trench formation occur along these plate boundaries or faults. The relative movement of the plates typically ranges from zero to 100 mm annually (Read & Watson 1975).

Tectonic plates are composed of oceanic lithosphere and thicker continental lithosphere, each topped by its own kind of crust. Along convergent boundaries, subduction, or one plate moving under another, carries the lower one down into the mantle; the material lost is roughly balanced by the formation of new oceanic crust along divergent margins by seafloor spreading. In this way, the total surface of the lithosphere remains the same. This prediction of plate

CHAPTER 1. OVERVIEW OF EARTHQUAKE

tectonics is also referred to as the conveyor belt principle. Earlier theories, since disproven, proposed gradual shrinking (contraction) or gradual expansion of the globe (Scalera & Lavecchia 2006).

Tectonic plates are able to move because the Earth's lithosphere has greater mechanical strength than the underlying asthenosphere. Lateral density variations in the mantle result in convection; that is, the slow creeping motion of Earth's solid mantle. Plate movement is thought to be driven by a combination of the motion of the seafloor away from spreading ridges due to variations in topography (the ridge is a topographic high) and density changes in the crust (density increases as newly formed crust cools and moves away from the ridge). At subduction zones the relatively cold, dense crust is "pulled" or sinks down into the mantle over the downward convecting limb of a mantle. Another explanation lies in the different forces generated by tidal forces of the Sun and Moon. The relative importance of each of these factors and their relationship to each other is unclear, and still the subject of much debate.

Figure 3. Tectonic plates boundaries

Three types of plate boundaries exist (Meissner 2002, p.100), with a fourth, mixed type, characterized by the way the plates move relative to each other. They

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are associated with different types of surface phenomena. The different types of plate boundaries are (USGS. Retrieved 12 June 2010):

1.2.1 Transform boundaries

(Conservative) occur where two lithospheric plates slide, or perhaps more accurately, grind past each other along transform faults, where plates are neither created nor destroyed. The relative motion of the two plates is either sinistral (left side toward the observer) or dextral (right side toward the observer). Transform faults occur across a spreading center. Strong earthquakes can occur along a fault. The San Andreas fault in California is an example of a transform boundary exhibiting dextral motion.

Figure 4. Transform boundaries

1.2.2 Divergent boundaries

(Constructive) occur where two plates slide apart from each other. At zones of ocean-to-ocean rifting, divergent boundaries form by seafloor spreading, allowing for the formation of new ocean basin. As the ocean plate splits, the ridge forms at the spreading center, the ocean basin expands, and finally, the plate area increases causing many small volcanoes and/or shallow earthquakes. At zones of continent-to-continent rifting, divergent boundaries

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may cause new ocean basin to form as the continent splits, spreads, the central rift collapses, and ocean fills the basin. Active zones of mid-ocean ridges (e.g., the Mid-Atlantic Ridge and East Pacific Rise), and continent-to-continent rifting (such as Africa's East African Rift and Valley and the Red Sea), are examples of divergent boundaries.

Figure 5. Divergent boundaries

1.2.3 Convergent boundaries

(Destructive) or *(active margins)* occur where two plates slide toward each other to form either a subduction zone (one plate moving underneath the other) or a continental collision. At zones of ocean-to-continent subduction (e.g. the Andes mountain range in South America, and the Cascade Mountains in Western United States), the dense oceanic lithosphere plunges beneath the less dense continent. Earthquakes trace the path of the downward-moving plate as it descends into asthenosphere, a trench forms, and as the subducted plate is heated it releases volatiles, mostly water from hydrous minerals, into the surrounding mantle. The addition of water lowers the melting point of the mantle material above the subducting slab, causing it to melt. The magma that results typically leads to volcanism (Grove, Timothy 2012). At zones of ocean-to-ocean

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subduction (e.g. Aleutian islands, Mariana islands, and the Japanese islands arc), older, cooler, denser crust slips beneath less dense crust. This motion causes earthquakes and a deep trench to form in an arc shape. The upper mantle of the subducted plate then heats and magma rises to form curving chains of volcanic islands. Deep marine trenches are typically associated with subduction zones, and the basins that develop along the active boundary are often called "foreland basins". Closure of ocean basins can occur at continent-to-continent boundaries (e.g., Himalayas and Alps): collision between masses of granitic continental lithosphere; neither mass is subducted; plate edges are compressed, folded, uplifted.

Figure 6. Convergent boundaries

Plate boundary zones occur where the effects of the interactions are unclear, and the boundaries, usually occurring along a broad belt, are not well defined and may show various types of movements in different episodes.

1.3 Methods for earthquake prediction

Earthquake processes according to Asada [21] include:

- Buildup of elastic strain
- Dilatancy and development of cracks

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- Influx of water and unstable deformation in the fault zone
- Fault rupture of the earthquake
- Sudden drop in stress followed by aftershocks

It was stated by the same author that concentration of radon in ground water does not change much under normal conditions. Radon emissions increase during stage II of an earthquake, and then levels off during stage III. During stage II, microcracks form in the rocks resulting in an increase in the surface area of the rocks. The increased surface area exposes more of the radon to water, which would cause a greater breakdown of the radioactive mineral. Radon emissions increase as the radon is washed out of the rock during stage II. As the water returns during stage III, radon emissions would level off because microcracks stop forming. The newly formed microcracks serve as pathways for more of the radon gas to escape to the surface; this results in higher radon emissions.

1.3.1 Animal behavior

For centuries there have been anecdotal accounts of anomalous animal behavior preceding and associated with earthquakes. In cases where animals display unusual behavior some tens of seconds prior to a quake, it has been suggested they are responding to the P-wave [22]. These travel through the ground about twice as fast as the S-waves that cause most severe shaking [23]. They predict not the earthquake itself that has already happened but only the imminent arrival of the more destructive S-waves. It has also been suggested that unusual behavior hours or even days beforehand could be triggered by foreshock activity at magnitudes that most people do not notice [24]. Another confounding factor of accounts of unusual phenomena is skewing due to "flashbulb memories" otherwise unremarkable details become more memorable and more significant when associated with an emotionally powerful event such as an earthquake [25]. A study that attempted to control for these kinds of factors found an increase in unusual animal behavior (possibly triggered by foreshocks) in one case, but not in four other cases of seemingly similar earthquakes [26].

1.3.2 Changes in V_p/V_s

V_p is the symbol for the velocity of a seismic "P" (primary or pressure) wave passing through rock, while V_s is the symbol for the velocity of the "S" (secondary or shear) wave. Small-scale laboratory experiments have shown that the ratio of these two velocities – represented as V_p/V_s – changes when rock is near the point of fracturing. In the 1970s it was considered a likely breakthrough when Russian seismologists reported observing such changes later discounted [27] in the region of a subsequent earthquake [28]. This effect, as well as other possible precursors, has been attributed to dilatancy, where rock stressed to near its breaking point expands (dilates) slightly [29]. Study of this phenomenon near Blue mountain lake in New York state led to a successful albeit informal prediction in 1973 [30], and it was credited for predicting the 1974 Riverside (CA) quake [31]. However, additional successes have not followed, and it has been suggested that these predictions were a flukes [32]. A V_p/V_s anomaly was the basis of a 1976 prediction of a M 5.5 to 6.5 earthquake near Los Angeles, which failed to occur [33]. Other studies relying on quarry blasts (more precise, and repeatable) found no such variations [34], while an analysis of two earthquakes in California found that the variations reported were more likely caused by other factors, including retrospective selection of data [35]. Geller 1997 noted that reports of significant velocity changes have ceased since about 1980.

1.3.3 Radon emission

Most rock contains small amounts of gases that can be isotopically distinguished from the normal atmospheric gases. There are reports of spikes in the concentrations of such gases prior to a major earthquake; this has been attributed to release due to pre-seismic stress or fracturing of the rock. One of these gases is radon, produced by radioactive decay of the trace amounts of uranium present in most rock [36]. Radon is useful as a potential earthquake predictor because it is radioactive and thus easily detected [37], and its short half-life 3.8 days makes radon levels sensitive to short-term fluctuations. A 2009 review [38]–found 125 reports of changes in radon emissions prior to 86

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earthquakes since 1966. But as the ICEF found in its review, the earthquakes with which these changes are supposedly linked were up to a thousand kilometers away, months later, and at all magnitudes. In some cases the anomalies were observed at a distant site, but not at closer sites. The ICEF found "no significant correlation" [39]. Another review concluded that in some cases changes in radon levels preceded an earthquake, but a correlation is not yet firmly established [40].

1.3.4 Electromagnetic anomalies

Observations of electromagnetic disturbances and their attribution to the earthquake failure process go back as far as the Great Lisbon earthquake of 1755, but practically all such observations prior to the mid-1960s are invalid because the instruments used were sensitive to physical movement [41]. Since then various anomalous electrical, electric-resistive, and magnetic phenomena have been attributed to precursory stress and strain changes that precede earthquakes [42], raising hopes for finding a reliable earthquake precursor [43]. While a handful of researchers have gained much attention with either theories of how such phenomena might be generated, claims of having observed such phenomena prior to an earthquake, no such phenomena has been shown to be an actual precursor.

A 2011 review [44] found the "most convincing" electromagnetic precursors to be ULF magnetic anomalies, such as the Corralito's event (discussed below) recorded before the 1989 Loma Prieta earthquake. However, it is now believed that observation was a system malfunction. Study of the closely monitored 2004 Parkfield earthquake found no evidence of precursory electromagnetic signals of any type; further study showed that earthquakes with magnitudes less than 5 do not produce significant transient signals [45]. The International Commission on Earthquake Forecasting for Civil Protection (ICEF) considered the search for useful precursors to have been unsuccessful [46].

1.3.5 Dilatancy-diffusion

In the 1970s the dilatancy–diffusion hypothesis was highly regarded as providing a physical basis for various phenomena seen as possible earthquake precursors [47]. It was based on "solid and repeatable evidence" [48] from laboratory experiments that highly stressed crystalline rock experienced a change in volume, or dilatancy, [49] which causes changes in other characteristics, such as seismic velocity and electrical resistivity, and even large-scale uplifts of topography. It was believed this happened in a 'preparatory phase' just prior to the earthquake, and that suitable monitoring could therefore warn of an impending quake.

Detection of variations in the relative velocities of the primary and secondary seismic waves expressed as V_p/V_s – as they passed through a certain zone was the basis for predicting the 1973 Blue Mountain Lake (NY) and 1974 Riverside (CA) quake [50]. Although these predictions were informal and even trivial, their apparent success was seen as confirmation of both dilatancy and the existence of a preparatory process, leading to what were subsequently called "wildly over-optimistic statements" [51] that successful earthquake prediction "appears to be on the verge of practical reality [52].

However, many studies questioned these results [53], and the hypothesis eventually languished. Subsequent study showed it failed for several reasons, largely associated with the validity of the assumptions on which it was based", including the assumption that laboratory results can be scaled up to the real world [54]. Another factor was the bias of retrospective selection of criteria [55]. Other studies have shown dilatancy to be so negligible that Main et. Al, concluded: "The concept of a large-scale 'preparation zone' indicating the likely magnitude of a future event, remains as ethereal as the ether that went undetected in the Michelson-Morley experiment.

1.4 Active faults determine by radon gas

1.4.1 Diffusion Processes

Diffusion is the mechanism of radon release from mineral grains due to differences in the concentration of the substance; radon moves from areas whose a greater concentration in to lower concentration areas. Diffusional Movement is one of the major mechanisms of radon release from mineral grains (emanation), which is caused by a concentration gradient. Diffusion essentially occurs where the radon relatively moves to the fluid in the rock. The Diffusion coefficient depends on parameters such as porosity, permeability and fluid content of various media. Radon gas that was formed from radium decaying would escape from the minerals rock then diffuses in the crevices of rocks and soil formed part of the soil gas. Radon gas which was in the near earth's surface would escape into the atmosphere and to be part of the air, so that radon gas to be tenuous near surface because it seemly always pumped out into the air and there was a gradient density of radon gas. Radon gas which is closer to the earth's surface tenuous than below depth which is originally the radon gas come from. Thus, the general diffusion of radon gas will occur continuously from depth of subsurface to the earth's surface.

1.4.2 Convection Process

Convection is transport mechanism fluid (liquid or gas) to move and "bring" a radon. According to [56], ^{222}Rn element cannot be taken from the depth to the surface only by diffusion alone, but also be done by the convective motion in the fluid carrier, so that ^{222}Rn can carry information about the geological environment that lies in the depths up to the surface. Convective transport mechanism should be highlighted because that can be used to explain how radon can migrate at a significant distance. This migration in the subsurface can be considered to have lateral and vertical components that can be represented by the both lateral flow of groundwater and soil gas vertical motion. An important concept of convection introduced by [57] which stated that radon brought to the surface by convection. A generated convection cells by subsurface temperature gradient (either in water gas or soil gas) caused the hot fluid move

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up and cold fluid conversely move down. This is because the hot fluid has a lighter mass/density than cold fluid. Movement of soil gas was induced and enhanced by heating result in density declining. It is also dependent on temperature and soil permeability, which determined how far radon can be transported. Reference [58] considered for the case of a thermal gradient "normal" 30 °C/km that result a vertical distance convection through 100 m can be reached for air or water in the sand (hydraulic conductivity, $K > 3 \times 10^{-7} / \text{cm}^2$) and as far as 300 m for $K > 3 \cdot 10^{-8} / \text{cm}^2$ that could apply to sand and soil and high permeability sandstone within range for basal permeability (10^{-5} to $10^{-9} / \text{cm}^2$). They also concluded that in higher areas permeability than its normal, fluid convection induced by thermal subterrestrial is a potential transport mechanism. In Reference [59] stated that radon was transported by convective fluid could detectable over 100 m distance, as long as the velocity fluid is higher than 100 m per day (0.12 cm/s) [60]. In depth of the earth of the geothermal area, a fluid derived from meteoric water was contact with magmatic rocks caused fluid heated and reacts (physically or chemically) with elements in magmatic rocks such as uranium. The hot fluid below the surface moves upward due to a temperature gradient towards the surface whose lower temperature, but the it was trapped in the reservoir due to the impermeable caprock layer. High pressure fluid heated that uranium or radium containing could moved up to the earth's surface through cracks or faults. Because radon is a daughter element produced constantly by Radium through radioactive decay in uranium chain, it can be explained by simply how radon rises to the surface [60].

1.4.3 Radon as a Exploration Methods

There are three isotopes of radon is often occur in nature i.e. ^{222}Rn (radon) with a half-life time of 3825 days, ^{220}Rn (thoron) with a half-life of 54.5 seconds and ^{219}Rn (actinon) with a half-life of 4 seconds. Radon choosed as an exploration tool because of a suitable half-life and its source in the form of magmatic rocks derived from the decay of ^{238}U series while thoron decay series derived from thorium. Radon is a unique element in the chain of radioactive uranium decay wich very different from other radioactive properties. It is able to be detected in very low concentrations. So, this became a basis for

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the highly sensitive geochemical methods [61]. In addition, there are several other reasons why radon is used as a tracer element as in [62] (i) To represent the thermodynamic activity. It is transported to the surface by geothermal gas in place where the thermodynamic activity is high. (ii) To indicate active faults and fractures. It moved faster when passing through open fractures or fracture. (iii) No correction required for the geochemical composition. As a noble gas, it is mixed with no other elements in the field. (iv) To show recent geothermal activity because the new radon generated every 20 days [60]. Radon also can be used to refer high permeability and high heat flow areas because it is a noble gas and easily soluble in water. High values of total radon counts on surface will be taken to indicate fracture zones or cracks where the isotopes can migrate to the surface faster. In the system of hydrothermal geothermal field, the natural liquid (a mixture of steam, gas and liquid fluid) forced to the surface in the convective process. This situation inspired the utility of ^{222}Rn as a natural tracer. High temperature fluid carried ^{222}Rn by convection to the surface through cracks and crashed in the rocks along the fault. Radon in geothermal fluids is a function of the distribution of porosity and cracks in geothermal reservoir. Locations where radon achieve surface faster, it could be an indication of a higher permeability zone [60]

1.5 Geophysical tools of Ulaanbaatar

Over the years 2012 and 2013, total of 42 seismic activity monitoring stations were installed around Ulaanbaatar city area. In these, 16 long-period earthquake recording, 7 GPS, regional geodynamics and tectonic movement prior to strong earthquake monitoring, changes in earth's magnetic field recording 3, surface displacement monitoring 6, strainmeter's 1 that studies the strain along active faults and around Ulaanbaatar city active faults, 8 radon measuring stations are currently in operation. Data of geophysical stations that are close to Ulaanbaatar city is transferred by UHF modem to the RELAY station. Data of the stations that are located far away from the city is connected to the high speed 3G server of mobile carriers, making it easier to monitor and study those data. Regional earthquake mechanism, pattern and prediction studies are being enabled by installations of these geophysical monitoring stations.

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Under the project “In depth research of seismic active zone around Ulaanbaatar city”, GURALP CMG-3ESPC long-period seismometer and GURALP CMG-DM24s3-EAM digitizer on 16 locations were installed in 2013. Since 2008, 5 earthquake monitoring short-period stations have been in operation. 11 of them are connected to a perpetual radio transfer server and the rest are connected to high speed 3G server provided by mobile carriers Mobicom, Skytel, Unitel and Gmobile. IAG’s National Data Center is monitoring the seismic activity around Ulaanbaatar city continuously.

Figure 7. Seismic stations position of near Ulaanbaatar

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Figure 8. This map shown by around of Ulaanabaatar city Gps stations. Blue point is gps stations, red line is active faults.

Figure 9. All tiltmeter stations position. Blue point is tiltmeter stations, Red line is an active faults.

Soil monitoring of radon is believed to be able to detect earthquakes specific time before they occur, according to many scientists around the world. The institute of Astronomy and Geophysics installed 8 radon probes on the Khustain and Emeelt seismic faults which are very close to the city (respectively 130 km and 20 km far from the city). The institute focuses its research on 2 probes placed right on the seismic activity fault of Khustain, 5 probes on the

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seismic activity fault of Emeelt and another probe which is not on a fault. The probes on the Khustai fault didn't show any anomaly of radon activity since their installation (in 2012), but the Emeelt probes (installed in July 2009) measured many anomalies of radon activity. Khustai fault has only few earthquakes and Emeelt fault is very active around 500 earthquakes each year. All these earthquakes have low magnitudes. During the last two years, every time that the probes on Emeelt fault measured anomalies in radon activity, several shocks happened around 20 days later. Those results are currently discussed amongst the scientific community to determine whether radon is or is not a precursor of seismic activity.

Figure 10. Map of radon station. Shown by blue point is radon station, red line is active faults.

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Figure 11. This picture shows prepare to pvc tube

Figure 12. Before install in BMC2 detector

Figure 13. After installed BMC2 detector.

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2.1 Khustai fault

The Khustai range fault system is located about 10 km west of Ulaanbaatar city. The fault system consist of 4 sub-faults converging at the Ongot junction: the main Khustai fault (80 km long left-lateral strike-slip) the Dolootoyin fault (43 km long right-lateral strike-slip) the Lun fault (58 km long left-lateral-strike-slip) and the south Khustai fault (31 km long normal dip-slip). The last earthquake on a branch of the main segment has been dated about 1000 years ago. The rate of deformation on the main segment is estimated about 0.3-0.4 mm/years. If the age of the last event is confirmed on the main fault segment, the fault is ready to procedure a magnitude 7.8 today. Nevertheless, only the main central fault segment has been investigated in term of paleo-earthquake identification. [63]

2.2 Gunj fault

Around mid-1980, near the Gachuurt village, Ulaanbaatar city, in order to choose suitable location for water dam construction, geological study was done in west Ulaanbaatar. Russian scientists discovered an active fault at Gunj Resort 8 kilometers north of “Mongol Shiltgeen”. Even though Gunj fault was discovered, detailed research hasn’t been done. Through the project, Gunj fault has been researched with the results from north eastern Ulaanbaatar seismotectonic study. “Gunj’s tunnel” which resides through that fault is the reason why the fault is named after it.

2.3 Avdar fault

Avdar fault starts from Khundlun mountain, 70 kilometers from Ulaanbaatar downtown and goes all the way until Erdene mountain which covers total of 50 kilometers and oriented in N40⁰ direction. The closest distance from that fault to Ulaanbaatar city is 35 kilometers and from Dzun Mod, Tov province that distance is only 20 kilometers. On the Ulaanbaatar region geological map, it is noted as a boundary between different minerals, in other words, geological

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fault. Avdar fault is newly discovered active fault found from the results of a research project around the area. There has occurred a magnitude 4 earthquake on 22nd March, 2009 and the earthquake was felt by the residents of Dzun Mod and Ulaanbaatar. Seismogeological, geophysical research along with satellite imaging have been done at the area.

2.4 Mungunmorit fault

140 kilometers north east from Ulaanbaatar, Mungunmorit sum, Tov province, oriented from north to south, an active fault was first discovered by Russian scientists. Therefore, the activity was reassured by a quick research by US and Mongolian scientists. In 2013, based on the information above, detailed study has been done on the area by Mongolian scientists with the collaboration of the Irkutsk Crust Institute, Russia. Autumn of the year 2013, satellite images were taken in order to determine the general positioning and the shift movements of the fault. It was discovered that the fault is 100 kilometers long. Starting from 2010, there has been occurrences of strong and average earthquakes in the area.

2.5 Sharkhai fault

This 50 kilometers' long fault is oriented in 45⁰N and is located 35 kilometers south of Altanbulag, Tuv Province. The end of the fault is the Khoshigt's Khondii and the fault goes all the way till Nogoos Dov. Majority of the fault is located along the Sharkhai river and thus, it was named after it. The furthest distance from the fault to Ulaanbaatar is 70 kilometers but the east end is 40 kilometers away. Also, it is 19 kilometers away from Dzun Mod and only 7 kilometers away from the international airport in Khushigt's Kundii. Sharkai fault hasn't been studied before and it was first studied in detail by this project. Since 2005, there has been activities observed but it is rather less active compared to the Emeelt fault activity. Over the years 2012 and 2013, seismogeological, geophysical research and satellite imaging has been done at this the Sharkhai fault.

2.6 Emeelt fault

From 1994 to 2000, with the help from France and USA, 15 permanent high sensitivity seismic stations were constructed and by doing so 100 kilometers radius area around Ulaanbaatar has become available to be studied for its earthquake mechanism and its general standing. On average, there is 80 to 100 earthquakes recorded annually over the course of 10 years from 1994 to 2004. In this, on average, 10 to 20 earthquakes has been recorded in Ulaanbaatar city area. Starting from 2005, number of earthquakes that occurs in Ulaanbaatar has drastically increased and several earthquakes that are noticeable by human has occurred. For the last 5 years, there has been total of 3000 earthquakes and the ones that were noticeable by human are in 2008, 44 kilometers north of Ulaanbaatar, Batsumber, Tov Province, magnitude 4.2, 80 kilometers west of Ulaanbaatar, Khustai ridge, magnitude 3.9, in 2009, 70 kilometers south of the city, in Tov Province area, magnitude 4.0 and in 2013, west of Ulaanbaatar at the Emeelt train station, magnitude 3.7 earthquakes. In 2009 and 2010 the number of recorded earthquakes has increased and became even 508 and 628 each. From 2012 to 2013 the number was doubled from the previous years. First eleven months of the year 2012, total of 286 earthquakes were recorded and by the end of the year the number became 759 which was resulted from the activity of December 2012. Total of 2128 earthquakes occurred in 2013.

Pre-processing work was done with the use of “SPOT-5” and “Google earth” for the satellite image processing. By this processing, active fault 2 kilometers from Emeelt train station was discovered. However, this fault was exposed to major depreciation and was low on visibility therefore in the center of the activity region 1 to 2 kilometers long fault part was unable to be determined. For that reason, more detailed, cloudless and snowless imaging was done by 50 centimeters resolution black and white and 20 meters resolution multi-spectra “Plaiades” satellite imaging. This imaging enabled the discovery

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of 10 kilometers long part of the fault oriented in south east $N143^{\circ}$ direction.

Figure 14. Processing of "Plaiades" satellite images around the fault of the Emeelt

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Figure 15. Near of the Ulaanbaatar city active faults.

2.7 Radon gas and its properties

Radon is a naturally occurring noble gas, i.e., it is almost chemically inert or is not prone to combine with other atoms to create molecules. Radon has no color, odor or taste. It is soluble in water, and its solubility decreases with increasing temperature [64]. Density of radon is 9.73 g/l under standard conditions making it the heaviest gas in nature [65]. When cooled below its freezing point, radon has a brilliant phosphorescence which becomes yellow at lower temperatures and orange-red at the temperature of liquid air [66]. Radon is sometimes referred to as a metalloid element which lies on a diagonal between the true metals and nonmetals in the periodic table. It has some of the characteristics of both groups behaving similarly to boron, germanium, antimony and polonium [67].

Radon is absorbed in charcoal, silica-gel and similar substances. This allows to separate it from other gases. Radon can be effectively removed from a sample air stream by collecting it on activated charcoal cooled to the temperature of solid CO₂ (-78.5 °C) [68]. Radon is desorbed from charcoal by heating it up to 350 °C [65]. The most important feature of radon is its radioactivity. With atomic number of 86, radon has no stable isotopes. It is produced by the alpha decay of radium and by migrating in soil and water, can reach outdoor or indoor air. Typically, outdoor radon concentration near the ground level is about 0.13 pCi/l (approx. 4.8 Bq/m³) [64]. In the United States, the average outdoor radon concentration is about 0.4 pCi/l (approx. 15 Bq/m³) and the mean indoor concentration is 1.5 pCi/l (approx. 55 Bq/m³) [69]. For indoor radon concentrations the EPA recommends 4 pCi/l (148 Bq/m³) as a safe level. The concerns are explained by the fact that high concentrations of radon can cause lung cancer. Once radon or its daughters are inhaled, they can decay in the lungs. That results in emitting alpha particles, which produce intense ionizing radiation, and therefore, possess high relative biological effectiveness (RBE). It is especially important for mining and milling workers to monitor the radon exposure.

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The first recorded awareness of unusually high mortality from respiratory disease that turned out to be lung cancer was reported by Agricola for miners in the Erz Mountains of eastern Europe in 1556. However, the first association of lung cancer with miners was determined only in 1879. Finally, it was not until the 1950s that it was found that radon was the primary cause of lung cancer in miners [65]. It was reported by Saccomanno et al. [70] that radon and its daughters' levels in United States uranium mines were measured from 1950 to 1968 and ranged from 100 to 10,000 pCi/l (3,700 to 370,000 Bq/m³). These radon concentrations led to increased mortality among workers reported by Lundin et al. [68]. Uranium miners, exposed to lower radon levels of 50 to 150 pCi/l of air for about 10 years have shown an increased frequency of lung cancer [71].

2.8 Radon propagation in nature

Originated in the earth crust, radon can propagate in soil. Some of the radon atoms, while formed from radium, become trapped within the grain of rock or soil and are not able to escape into pore spaces for further propagation. The atoms that are not trapped can be absorbed in groundwater or diffuse through the soil and migrate. Fracturing and faulting of rocks can contribute to the radon migration. Cracks and ruptures can be freeway to soil gas molecules [72]. More detailed discussion on radon propagation in soil is given in section 6.2. The atoms of ²¹⁸Rn, ²¹⁹Rn, ²²⁰Rn, ²²²Rn can emanate from soil, uraniumiferous rocks and water and become dispersed in the air. Radon is a noble gas; this fact allows it to migrate by diffusion and convection without significant interaction with nitrogen, oxygen and other atoms in air. In the process of airborne radon decay, free atoms of polonium, lead, bismuth, astatine, thallium and mercury are produced. They are either positive or negative ions, depending on decay mode of the parent isotope: beta or alpha decay, respectively. The presence of charge allows the ions to be electrostatically attached to dust particles or aerosols. This is the main reason of why radon and its daughters account for half of the total radiation dose to human from all natural sources [73].

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The fact that radon is radioactive, and does not chemically react with other gases, makes it unique as a tracer for the studying various processes in the indoor and outdoor air [74]. The main mechanisms of transport in the atmosphere are horizontal winds, convection and eddy diffusion as used in tracer studies. Relatively high levels of radon encountered in caves have also been the target of studies as well as natural radon transport from earth to the atmosphere by volcanoes. The sharp contrast that occurs between ^{222}Rn flux from the oceans compared with land areas has led to the identification of significant differences in radon concentration over those parts of the continents where marine air masses are common [75]. Another radon application was described by Israel [76]; the rate at which ions are produced in the air, their electrical conductivity and mobility spectra are all affected by the concentration of ^{222}Rn , ^{220}Rn and their decay products. The ions created by decay of the radon daughters have been used to investigate the atmospheric electrical environments under fair weather and thunderstorm conditions [77].

2.9 Isotopes of Radon and decay chains

There are 39 known isotopes of radon with atomic mass numbers ranging from 193 to 231. The first discovered isotope was ^{222}Rn . In 1899, when P. Curie and M. Curie were studying radium samples, they reported a presence of unknown radioactive gas. It was identified by Friedrich Ernst Dorn in 1900 and named radium emanation. Radon was isolated as an element by M. Curie in 1908 [78]. The most recently identified isotopes, ^{230}Rn and ^{231}Rn , were discovered by H. Alvarez-Pol in 2010 [79]. Four isotopes, ^{218}Rn , ^{219}Rn , ^{220}Rn , ^{222}Rn are naturally occurring in decay chains of ^{238}U , ^{235}U and ^{232}Th , as shown in Figure 16. Uranium-238 decay chains, and Figure 13, Figure 14, respectively. ^{218}Rn is a daughter isotope ^{218}Rn of At, which is produced from Po. Both branches have low probabilities and are not shown in Figure 7. The most long-lived isotope is ^{222}Rn with a half-life of 3.8235(3) days [79].

It produces a series of short-lived radioactive products called progeny, or daughters. ^{222}Rn For instance, when some amount of Rn decays to Po, which is also radioactive and has half-life of 3.10 minutes [80], half of polonium atoms

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will decay in 3.10 minutes. Thus, ^{218}Po cannot accumulate, but it will reach an equilibrium amount. ^{218}Rn Since ^{218}Po half-life is much shorter than the one of ^{218}Rn , this example demonstrates a case of secular equilibrium. This means that after a period of time, quantity of polonium will remain constant (will decrease only due to decrease of radon amount). In this case, polonium production rate is equal to its decay rate. While moving down the decay chain, it is obvious, that the amount of each next isotope produced, depends on the activity of its parent. When the half-life of progeny is not short enough, compared to the parent's half-life, only transient equilibrium can be achieved. Finally, when the half-life of the daughter isotope is longer, than the one of the parents, no equilibrium can occur.

Figure 16. Uranium-238 decay chains

The Thorium-232 Decay Chain

Figure 17. Thorium-232 decay chains

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Figure 18. Uranium-235 decay chains

2.10 Radon Gas Origin

Naturally occurring radon originates from radium that is present in soil or rock. Radon seeps out of the ground from the ubiquitous uranium and thorium series. For ^{222}Rn , ^{226}Rn , ^{238}Rn examples, Rn is a progeny of Ra, which is finally characterized by the level of U in soil. This way, the rate of radon production in soil is influenced by the distribution of uranium in the earth's upper crust. The average concentration of uranium and thorium in the top 0.3 meter of soil is 1 ton and 3 tons, respectively, per square mile [81]. Radioactivity in soils is related to radioactivity in rocks from which the soil is formed. Since uranium and radium can be found throughout the earth's crust and radium is also soluble in water, radon is found virtually everywhere [82]. Due to a ^{222}Rn half-life of almost 4 days, it can migrate from its place of origin either by pores in soil or groundwater, being dissolved in it. Relatively high solubility of radon in water (230 cm³/kg) that accounts for its presence in substantial amounts in certain spring waters. Eventually, some atoms of radon escape into the atmosphere. Due to its wide distribution in the atmosphere, radon makes up a unique set of tracers for a variety of transport and mixing processes. Measured profiles of ^{222}Rn and ^{220}Rn above the earth's surface are in general agreement with those predicted by turbulent diffusion theory [65]. Details on radon propagation are described in the following section

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4.1 Theory Describing Radon Diffusion During Short-time Exposures

In this and in the next section diffusion of radon in an activated charcoal canister is described. To take into account the radioactivity of radon, and therefore loss in its concentration with time, the diffusion equation (4.1) must be rewritten as follows:

$$\frac{\partial C(r,t)}{\partial t} = D\Delta C(r,t) - \lambda C(r,t) \quad (4.1)$$

where C [activity/length³] denotes radon concentration in air; t is time; D [length²/time] is radon diffusion coefficient in activated charcoal; λ [time⁻¹] is the decay constant of radon.

Diffusion along the x and y axis can be ignored, because it does not change the concentration along canister depth. Considering diffusion only along z axis, the equation transforms into the following:

$$\frac{\partial C(z,t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C(z,t)}{\partial z^2} - \lambda C(z,t) \quad (4.2)$$

To solve this partial differential equation, boundary and initial conditions must be defined. The initial condition is simply zero radon concentration in activated charcoal at time $t = 0$:

$$C(z,0) = 0 \quad (4.3)$$

The first boundary condition can be stated as follows:

$$C(0,t) = fcpC(t) \quad (4.4)$$

where k denotes adsorption coefficient [length³/mass] and p [mass/length³] is the charcoal density. It is assumed that radon concentration in air is constant and equal to C_0 . In this case the first boundary condition becomes:

$$C(0,t) = fcpC_0 \quad (4.5)$$

The initial and first boundary conditions for activated charcoal canister geometry are illustrated in the top of the cylinder. The second boundary

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condition is related to the other end of the canister, at $z = l$ and indicates that radon cannot enter the bottom of the canister, so radon gas flux there equals zero:

$$\left(\frac{\partial C(z,t)}{\partial z}\right)_{z=l} = 0 \quad (4.6)$$

To solve the diffusion equation (4.2) for the initial and boundary conditions (4.3), (4.4), (4.5) for the case of short-term exposure of activated charcoal to radon, considering its constant concentration in air during exposure, it is necessary to define the range of short-term exposure. As described by Nikezic and Urosevic [83], short-term exposure of activated charcoal canister to radon lasts less than 3 days. In this case disintegration of radon can be ignored. Therefore, radon decay constant is equal to zero:

$$\frac{\partial C(z,t)}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C(z,t)}{\partial z^2} \quad (4.7)$$

Fourier's method of separation of variables can be applied to solve this equation. The function $C(z, t)$ can be represented as a product of two functions: $Z(z)$ and $D(t)$ where $Z(z)$ depends only on coordinate z , and $D(t)$ depends only on time t .

$$C(z, t) = Z(z)D(t) \quad (4.8)$$

Equation (4.7) requires $C(z, t)$ to be differentiated once with respect to time t on the left-hand side, and twice with respect to coordinate z on the right-hand side:

$$\frac{dC(z,t)}{dt} = \frac{d(Z(z)T(t))}{dt} = \frac{dZ(z)T(t)+Z(z)dT(t)}{dt} = \frac{Z(z)dT(t)}{dt} \quad (4.9)$$

$$\frac{d^2 C(z,t)}{dz^2} = \frac{d^2(Z(z)T(t))}{dz^2} = \frac{d(dZ(z)T(t)+Z(z)dT(t))}{dz^2} = \frac{d^2 Z(z)T(t)}{dz^2} \quad (4.10)$$

After substituting (4.9) and (4.10) in the equation (4.7):

$$\frac{Z(z)dT(t)}{dt} = D \frac{d^2 Z(z)T(t)}{dz^2} \quad (4.11)$$

After dividing both sides of the equation (4.6) by $DZ(z)T(t)$:

$$\frac{1}{DT(t)} \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = \frac{1}{Z(z)} \frac{d^2 Z(z)}{dz^2} \quad (4.12)$$

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Assuming that both sides of the equation are equal to certain constant $-a$:

$$\frac{1}{DT(t)} \frac{dT(t)}{dt} = -a^2 \quad (4.13)$$

$$\frac{1}{Z(z)} \frac{d^2Z(z)}{dz^2} = -a^2 \quad (4.14)$$

Solution to the equation (4.13) is

$$T(t) = C'e^{a^2Dt} \quad (4.15)$$

Solution to the equation (4.14) is

$$Z(z) = A \sin az + B \cos az \quad (4.16)$$

where C' , A and B are constants of integration.

The final solution according to equation (4.8) is a product of solutions of equations (4.15) and (4.16):

$$C(z, t) = C'e^{a^2Dt} (A \sin az + B \cos az + C_1z + C_2) \quad (4.17)$$

The last two terms appear since equation (4.7) is a second order differential equation. These terms vanish after double derivation on z as well as after derivation on t :

$$\frac{d^2C(z,t)}{dz^2} = \frac{d^2(C'e^{-a^2Dt}(A \sin az + B \cos az) + C_1z + C_2)}{dz^2} = \frac{d^2(C'e^{-a^2Dt}(A \sin az + B \cos az))}{dz^2} + 0 + 0 \quad (4.18)$$

$$\frac{dC(z,t)}{dt} = \frac{d(C'e^{-a^2Dt}(A \sin az + B \cos az) + C_1z + C_2)}{dt} = \frac{d(C'e^{-a^2Dt}(A \sin az + B \cos az))}{dt} + 0 + 0 \quad (4.19)$$

After applying the first boundary condition, equation (3.10), to the equation

(4.17):

$$C(0, t) = kpC_0 = BC'e^{-a^2Dt} + C_2 \quad (4.20)$$

Since the right-hand side of the equation depends on time and the left hand side is constant, then $B = 0$. The equation can be rewritten as follows:

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$$C_2 = kpC_0 \quad (4.21)$$

In this case solution becomes:

$$C(z, t) = kpC_0 + AC'e^{-a^2Dt} + \sin az + C_1z \quad (4.22)$$

After applying the second boundary condition (4.11):

$$\left(\frac{\partial C(z,t)}{\partial z}\right)_{z=l} = \left(\frac{\partial(kpC_0 + AC'e^{-a^2Dt} \sin az + C_1z)}{\partial z}\right)_{z=l} = \alpha AC'e^{-a^2Dt} \cos al + C_1 = 0 \quad (4.23)$$

This expression is true when $\cos al = 0$ and $C_1 = 0$

Therefore $al = \pi n + \frac{\pi}{2} = (2n + 1)\frac{\pi}{2}$ where $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, hence the solution is

$$C(z, t) = kpC_0 + AC'e^{\frac{(2n+1)^2}{4l^2}\pi^2vt} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} \quad (4.24)$$

This is a partial solution of equation (4.7) for conditions (4.8), (4.5), (4.6). According to the theory of linear differential equations, the general solution is the sum of all partial solutions:

$$C(z, t) = kpC_0 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C'_n e^{-\frac{(2n+1)^2}{4l^2}\pi^2Dt} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} \quad (4.25)$$

After applying initial condition (4.3):

$$C(z, 0) = kpC_0 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C'_n \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} = 0 \quad (4.26)$$

Constants C_n are Fourier development of the function $-kpC_0$:

$$C'_n = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l -kpC_0 \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} dz = -\frac{2kpC_0}{l} \left(-\frac{2l}{(2n+1)\pi} \cos \frac{(2n+1)\pi l}{2l} + \frac{2l}{(2n+1)\pi} \cos 0 \right) = -\frac{4kpC_0}{(2n+1)\pi} \quad (4.27)$$

In this case, substitution of (4.25) to equation (4.23) yields in:

$$C(z, t) = kpC_0 \left(1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)} e^{-(2n+1)^2\pi^2\frac{Dt}{4l^2}} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} \right) \quad (4.28)$$

This equation gives spatial end time-dependent distribution of radon absorbed in activated charcoal with the assumption that there is no decay of

radon and its concentration in air is constant. After introducing S as a cross section surface [length²] of charcoal canister, $C(z, t)$ is radon activity in layer $z+dz$ at the moment t . The total radon activity $L(t)$ [Bq] in activated charcoal can be obtained by integrating $C(z, t)$ along the canister length:

$$A(t) = S \int_0^l C(z, t) dz \quad (4. 29)$$

The result of integration is:

$$\begin{aligned} A(t) = S \int_0^l k p C_0 \left(1 - \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2n+1)} e^{-(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 \frac{Dt}{4l^2}} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} \right) dz = \\ S k p C_0 \left(l - 0 + \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{2l}{(2n+1)^2 \pi} e^{-(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 \frac{Dt}{4l^2}} \cos \frac{(2n+1)\pi l}{2l} - \right. \\ \left. \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{2l}{(2n+1)^2 \pi} e^{-(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 \frac{Dt}{4l^2}} \cos 0 \right) = S l k p C_0 \left(1 - \frac{8}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\frac{(2n+1)^2 \pi^2 Dt}{4l^2}}}{(2n+1)^2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4. 30)$$

This result represents the total radon activity absorbed in a layer of activated charcoal of the depth l and surface area S , in time t . This approach shows how diffusion theory can be used to determine the activity of radon in activated charcoal during short-time exposure. The next section describes the case of long-time exposure.

4.2 Theory Describing Radon Diffusion During Long-time Exposures

According to Nikezic and Urosevic [83] the long-term exposure of activated charcoal canister to radon lasts for more than half-life of ²²²Rn (approx. 3.8 days). Radon decay inside the charcoal cannot be ignored in this case and the diffusion equation (4.2) should be solved taking into account radon decay constant. Boundary and initial conditions are the same as for the short-time exposure case.

Equation (4.7) can be reduced to equation (4.12) by introducing the substitution

$$C(z, t) = u(z, t) e^{-\lambda t} \quad (4.31)$$

Solving equation (4.7) using the function $u(z, t)$ is analogous to the previous case and is not described in detail. The result for the concentration is:

$$C(z, t) = kpC_0 \left[\frac{\cosh \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{D}}(l-z)}{\cosh \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{D}}l} - \frac{D\pi}{l^2} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(2n+1)e^{-\left(\frac{(2n+1)^2\pi^2 D}{4l^2} + \lambda\right)t}}{\left(\frac{(2n+1)^2\pi^2 D}{4l^2} + \lambda\right)} \sin \frac{(2n+1)\pi z}{2l} \right] \quad (4.32)$$

which gives a spatial and temporal distribution of radon concentration in activated charcoal canister for the exposure time much longer than half-life of ^{222}Rn . The total activity can be obtained as for the short-time case by integrating the previous equation along the canister length and multiplying by the result by its surface area. Integration gives:

$$A(t) = SkpC_0 \left[\sqrt{\frac{D}{\lambda} \frac{\sinh \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{D}}l}{\cosh \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{D}}l}} - \frac{2D}{l} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-\left(\frac{(2n+1)^2\pi^2 D}{4l^2} + \lambda\right)t}}{\left(\frac{(2n+1)^2\pi^2 D}{4l^2} + \lambda\right)} \right] \quad (4.33)$$

In the case of very long exposure $t \rightarrow \infty$ and the second term on the right-hand side of the equation vanishes:

$$A_{\infty} = SkpC_0 \sqrt{\frac{D}{\lambda} \frac{\sinh \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{D}}l}{\cosh \sqrt{\frac{\lambda}{D}}l}} \quad (4.34)$$

This equation gives the maximum possible activity of radon absorbed in the activated charcoal canister with depth l and surface area S .

4.3 BMC radon detector

The radon enters a detection volume through three cellulose filters which trap all the solid daughter products. The sensor is an implanted silicon detector with a depleted depth of 100 μm and 400 mm^2 of sensitive area. It authorizes the counting by spectrometry of atoms of ^{222}Rn and its daughter products created in the detection volume (window set at between 1.5 MeV and 6 MeV). The calibration of the sensor enables the volumic activity of the ^{222}Rn to be calculated. Radon: 50 $\text{Bq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ per imp.h $^{-1}$ (typically) Range from 0 to 1 $\text{GBq}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$.

Figure 19. BMC detector for radon monitoring instrument

4.4 Calen photomultiplier

Radon exhalation was measured using the accumulation chamber method [84]. First, 5-10 cm of soil was scrubbed. Then an accumulation chamber of 18 L volume and 0.125 m^2 surface area was installed on the scrubbed area. Leakage was reduced by plastering the sides of the container with wet soil. After 1 h, the gas in the container was sampled by a Lucas scintillation flask [85] with a volume of 125 mL, previously evacuated to a pressure of about 40-80 hPa. The atmospheric pressure was 620 hPa at this elevation. The radon-222 concentration in the flask was then obtained from counting photoemissions after a waiting time of 3 h, the necessary delay to achieve radioactive equilibrium between radon-

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^{222}Rn gas and its short-lived daughters. The counting operation was performed with a CALEN_ photomultiplier from Algade. The radon exhalation flux F_{Rn} was obtained from the measured radon concentration using [84]: where V_{acc} is the container volume, S_{acc} its base surface area, T_{acc} the accumulation time (1 h), and CR_{Rn} the measured radon concentration at time T_{acc} . The point-to-point measurement error was dominated by the statistical error on the counting rate. In addition, when comparing with other experiments, a common systematic uncertainty of 5%, due to the absolute calibration of the scintillation flask, is to be added in quadrature to obtain the total error (noted as tot.)

The same scrubbing method was applied for the measurement of the carbon dioxide flux, using a smaller accumulation chamber of 5 L volume and 0.053 m² surface area. We used a smaller accumulation chamber for CO₂ flux because it was easier to scrub soil on small surface. The concentration of carbon dioxide in the container was measured using a TESTO-235_ infrared sensor whose calibration had been checked in the laboratory. The concentration of carbon dioxide was recorded manually as a function of time, with time interval of 30 s, with a maximum accumulation time varying from 10 to 20 min. The concentration $c(t)$ as a function of time was then fitted using the function: where F was the carbon dioxide flux, c_0 a baseline concentration, and λ_0 the removal rate. The flux F was then converted into gm day [86], without applying further corrections. With this simplified method, we focused on the search of anomalous locations. The error on the flux F was dominated here by the uncertainty on the estimation of the slope of the concentration versus time. The resulting point-to-point uncertainty varied from 15 to 25%, which was sufficient for our purpose. When comparing with other experiments, a conservative systematic uncertainty of 25% is to be added in quadrature, also noted as (tot.).

Figure 20. Calen photomultiplier radon measurement instrument

CHAPTER 4. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

5.1 Data collection

We first installed radon detector along the Emeelt fault in 2009 and as of now 8 detectors are already installed and in working order, collecting data and those data is being analyzed. Natural radioactive radon gas is not only caused by earthquake but by humidity and soil and air temperature so we were able to collect precipitation and weather information as well.

5.2 BMC detector results

Results from the radon station data collected since 2009 will be displayed in this section. Stations EM01, EM02 and EM03 are the most interesting because they reported the highest level of anomaly. The region those stations were installed is 50km from Ulaanbaatar city and is most seismic active region. For instance, the mean amount of radon for EM01 is 5Bq/m^3 (Fig 21), for EM02 is 10Bq/m^3 (Fig 22) and for EM03 is the highest 20Bq/m^3 (Fig 23) and the station is the closest to Emeelt's seismic activity. EM04(Fig 24) and EM05(Fig 25) stations haven't given any visible anomaly yet since their installation in 2015. H04(Fig 26) station hasn't given noticeable anomaly and variation but station H05(Fig 27) recorded temperature dependent variation. To ensure the radon anomaly recorded for station EM03, additional station was installed and a correlation was done.

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Figure 21. This graph shown by EM01 station radon activity 2009 to 2018 September. Black line is radon activity red line is soil temperature.

Figure 22. EM02 station's data from 2010 until 2018/09. Red line is radon activity and black line is soil temperature

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Figure 23. EM03 station's data compared to soil temperature

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Figure 24. EM04 station's data compared to soil temperature. This station was installed around emeelt's seismic active area in 2015/06

Figure 25. EM05 station's data compared to soil temperature

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Figure 26. H04, the Hustai's radon station's data. Green line is radon activity
black line is soil temperature

Figure 27. H05 station radon activity. Shown by orange line is radon, black
line is soil temperature

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Figure 28. This figure shown by EM01, 02, 03 and EM06 station radon information and earthquake per day. Red line is EM01, green line is EM02, black is EM03, black dot is Earthquake per day, blue line is rainfall information.

We have noticed that quite a few radon anomalies were directly dependent on earthquake activity. A few instances before the earthquake swarm, the radon activity increases, but also for some instances of earthquake swarm the radon activity increased after. (Fig 28)

Figure 29. EM03 station's data is compared to air and soil temperature

We have observed that in the spring of every year, the radon activity increases. These anomalies happen when the soil temperature reaches around -5 degree Celsius and it draws our attention. We predict that when the snow melts and humid reaches the detector and the radon gas is brought down. (Fig 29).

5.3 Calen detector results

In 200*, in order to study Emeelt fault in detail, we first chose a place called Ehen-Us in 20th khoroo, Songinohairhan district to conduct fault trench study. Last time, in September 2018, at that place, we conducted fault mapping and radioactive radon gas study. To keep the result of radon gas measurement consistent, the measurements were performed under the same weather condition. Measurements were done in total of 5 profiles at 180 points and results were processed.

Figure 30. This figure shown by Emeelt fault and radon measurement points. Red line is shown Emeelt fault, cyan points are shown by radon points.

Figure 31. This figure shown by result of radon measurement. Red line is fault line, red point is trench fault line, red colored area is high activity radon gas.

In this figure, all measurement result values are depicted in various colors, deep blue color represents the lowest radon activity which is 80-450 Bq m^{-3} , light blue and green colors are the mean value of radon activity which is 1000-2500 Bq m^{-3} , and red color represents the highest activity which is over 3500 Bq m^{-3} . Out of the total 5 profile measurements, a high radon activity points were found in 1 to 4 profiles and when we associate it with the new trench study fault line it overlaps.

Figure 32. The result of Emeelt new trench in September 2018.

5.4 Conclusion

1. Results from consistent monitoring of radon gas indicates that the radon anomalies are connected in some way to the earthquake activity and atmosphere temperature.
2. Radon anomalies were visible when the soil temperature reaches -5 degree Celsius in the spring for the station EM03.
3. H05 has temperature dependent annual variation.
4. The highest radon anomaly is recorded at the station EM03 and the reason behind is that this station is the closest one to the Emeelt's earthquake epicenter.
5. H04 and H05 stations are no anomalies because this area has no seismic activity.
6. The Emeelt fault line is connected to radon measurement high anomalies. 4 profile measurements are have high anomaly. There are 2 times high to average.
7. We detected fault line in the trench. That line is near of the profile 4 high anomaly.

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